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1. Executive Summary

This report documents the GUTTA project financial progress during the reporting period ranging from 2019-07-01 to 2019-12-31, also termed in the following RP2. Please note that full reporting information is declared on SIU and the present report just represents an overview of its key contents. Moreover, the report does not take into account possible modifications to the present conditions, which may rise during the work of the FLCs.

When not re-defined here, shortcuts refer to the public GUTTA Glossary, which is found at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3676344>

2. Project progress

The report is organized into General achievements (Sect. 2.1), and Unforeseen Issues (Sect. 2.2).

2.1 General achievements

Expenditures for RP2 were regularly reported by CMCC, CSA and UniZd in SIU, in consideration of the main activities performed during the period. Costs were incurred in all budget lines.

With respect to the AF financial planning, expenditures are generally occurring in a regular manner, with the exception of PP4-MMPI and PP5-AdSP, which do not report any costs in this RP2, as also occurred in RP1.

Small adjustments of partners (CSA, UniZd and AdSP) budget are reported in the RP2 documentation for minor changes.

The overall financial progress, both at WP and budget line levels, is summarized in Fig.1-2.

Figure 1: Financial implementation status of GUTTA WPs. Following RP1, WP4 started in advance with respect to AF timeline. Blue is the absorbed fraction of the budget, cumulative of both RP1 and RP2; orange is the cumulative missing fraction within the current RP, and grey is the remaining fraction until the end of the project.

The WP-breakdown (Fig.1) highlights a major absorption gap in WP3, which was supposed to end with RP2. This is mainly due to the staff costs not claimed by PP4 and PP5 and to a partial redistribution of CMCC staff costs among WPs (with more resources dedicated to WP1 Management). Also, WP2 (Communication) suffers from underspending, as its leader Partner (PP4) has not reported any costs for RP2. The overall project absorption rate, defined as cumulative by expected absorption, reads 72.6%.

The breakdown of the financial absorption into budget lines (Fig.2) shows underspending in Staff category as predictable due to the missing costs of PP4 and PP5 during RP1 and RP2. Also “External Expertise and Services” category shows an insufficient progress due to the missing expenses of PP4 and PP5, but also of lower expenditures than planned by PP3-UniZd (regarding mainly WP2, in reference to the reduced costs of brochures production) and for CMCC (for reduced costs of FLC in WP1 and for postponement of WP2 expenses related to brochures printing and radio/tv spots). “Travel and Accommodation” is also lower than expected, and this is due not only to the missing expenses of two

PPs but also to the combination of the EC-day with the SCm1 (1st SC meeting), as both took place in Zagreb on Sept. 30- Oct2, 2019.

Figure 2: Breakdown of financial implementation status of GUTTA through budget lines. Color codes as in Fig.1

2.2 Unforeseen issues

2.2.1 CSA

- Minor budget amendments were requested and are included in the RP documentation.

2.2.2 UniZd

- Minor budget amendments were requested and are included in the RP documentation.

2.2.3 MMPI

- No costs were claimed in RP2, despite activities were performed and reported.

2.2.4 AdSP

- Minor budget amendments were requested and are included in the RP documentation. However, no costs were claimed in RP2.

3. Conclusions

The financial absorption of GUTTA project in RP2 was less than expected by about one quarter.

This is mainly due to the fact that no expenses were claimed by two Project Partners: MMPI and AdSP, continuing what happened in RP1.

Therefore, pending issues for upcoming RP3 include:

- a) Recovering of costs not declared in both RP1 and RP2 by MMPI and by AdSP
- b) Appointment of a FLC by AdSP
- c) Rearrangement of costs allocation among partners due to an update of activities responsibility, through a major amendment request

These points will be also addressed during the next Steering Committee meeting (SCm2), planned for April 1-2, 2020 as a teleconference (due to the ongoing COVID-19 outbreak in Europe).